

Lithium-Ion Battery State-of-Health Estimation Using Deep Learning

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Abstract—Lithium-ion batteries are widely used in portable devices, electric vehicles, energy storage systems, and industrial applications. However, their performance gradually decreases because of calendar aging and cycle aging, leading to capacity fade and increased internal resistance. Accurate state-of-health (SoH) estimation is therefore important for battery management, safety, and lifetime extension. This study investigates the use of deep learning, particularly a one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D-CNN), for estimating lithium-ion battery SoH from electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) data. The dataset contains impedance measurements from multiple battery cells under different test conditions. After preprocessing, complete impedance spectra are formed and divided into training and testing sets using a cell-based split to reduce information leakage. The results show that the model can learn the general relationship between impedance spectra and battery degradation. The trained model achieves relatively low average prediction errors, although its ability to capture the full variability of SoH is limited, especially for less frequent degradation ranges. Overall, the work demonstrates the potential of 1D-CNN models for EIS-based battery-health estimation while highlighting the importance of data balance and generalization in future development.

Index Terms—lithium-ion battery, state of health, SoH, deep learning, 1D-CNN, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, EIS, data-driven modeling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Lithium-ion batteries have become one of the most important electrochemical energy storage technologies in recent decades. They are widely used in electric vehicles, energy storage systems, portable electronic devices, and industrial applications because of their high energy density, efficiency, acceptable lifetime, and strong overall performance [1].

Despite these advantages, battery performance decreases over time. This degradation is mainly reflected in a reduction in usable capacity and an increase in internal resistance [2]. For this reason, continuous battery-health monitoring is essential for safe and efficient operation.

One of the most important indicators of battery condition is the state of health (SoH). SoH describes how the current performance of a battery compares with its initial healthy state. Accurate SoH estimation can support better decisions in battery management systems (BMSs), such as adjusting charging current, limiting operation under harmful conditions, and preventing further degradation [3].

In recent years, deep learning methods have attracted increasing attention for SoH estimation. These methods can model complex and nonlinear relationships between battery

measurements and degradation behavior [4]. For example, Sahajpal et al. [5] proposed a hybrid bidirectional recurrent network and one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D-CNN-BiRNN) for SoH estimation using voltage relaxation statistics. Alharbi et al. [6] compared centralized and decentralized approaches based on 1D-CNN, CNN-LSTM, and CNN-GRU models using the NASA battery dataset, showing strong performance for 1D-CNN. Zhang et al. [7] used a 1D-CNN model with Bayesian optimization for SoH estimation based on relaxation voltage profiles. Mazzi et al. [8] proposed a hybrid 1D-CNN and bidirectional gated recurrent unit model using current, voltage, and temperature inputs from BMS data. Li et al. [9] introduced an end-to-end neural network framework for joint SoH estimation and remaining useful life prediction.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the background of lithium-ion batteries and SoH estimation methods. Section III describes the dataset, preprocessing workflow, model architecture, training procedure, and results. Section IV discusses the results, limitations, and future improvements. Section V concludes the study.

II. BACKGROUND

Lithium-ion battery operation is based on the movement of lithium ions between two electrodes. In normal operation, lithium ions are stored in electrode materials rather than existing as free metallic lithium, which improves safety and cyclability [10].

A lithium-ion cell consists mainly of an anode, a cathode, an electrolyte, and a separator. The anode is commonly made of graphite, while the cathode is often made of lithium oxide compounds, such as lithium iron phosphate (LiFePO_4) or lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (LiNiMnCoO_2). During charging, lithium ions move from the cathode to the anode through the electrolyte. During discharging, they move back to the cathode. The electrolyte allows ion transport between electrodes, while the separator prevents direct contact between the anode and the cathode [11].

A. Aging Mechanisms

Lithium-ion batteries experience performance degradation over time. This degradation is usually observed through capacity loss and increased internal resistance. These changes are caused by side reactions and other degradation processes inside the cell [11].

Battery aging is commonly divided into two main categories:

- *Calendar aging*: Calendar aging occurs even when the battery is not actively used. High state of charge, elevated temperature, and long storage time can accelerate side reactions and capacity loss [2], [12].
- *Cycle aging*: Cycle aging results from repeated charging and discharging. The depth of charge, current level, temperature, and operating profile influence the intensity of this aging process. Harsh operating conditions, such as high current and elevated temperature, can damage electrode structures and accelerate degradation [2], [12].

B. Definition of SoH

State of health is a measure of battery degradation relative to the initial state of the battery. It is widely used to evaluate battery aging and usability in practical applications [1], [3].

1) *Capacity-Based SoH*: The most common definition of SoH is based on usable capacity. In this case, SoH is defined as the ratio between the current capacity and the rated capacity of the battery [3]:

$$SoH = \frac{C_{current}}{C_{rated}} \times 100, \quad (1)$$

where $C_{current}$ is the current usable capacity and C_{rated} is the rated capacity. As the battery loses capacity, its SoH decreases. In many applications, a battery is considered to reach end of life when its SoH falls to approximately 80% [1].

2) *Resistance-Based SoH*: Internal resistance also increases as a battery ages. In resistance-based SoH estimation, the health state is evaluated by comparing the current internal resistance with the initial and end-of-life resistance values. This approach is particularly important in high-power applications, where increased resistance reduces output power and increases heat generation [1], [3]. Resistance-based SoH can be written as [8]:

$$SoH = \frac{R_{EOL} - R_k}{R_{EOL} - R_0} \times 100, \quad (2)$$

where R_{EOL} is the internal resistance at end of life, R_k is the resistance at the current cycle, and R_0 is the resistance at the beginning of life.

C. Methods for SoH Estimation

SoH estimation methods can be divided into two broad categories: direct measurement-based methods and indirect analysis methods, as shown in Fig. 1. Direct methods include Coulomb counting, internal resistance measurement, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. Indirect methods include model-based, data-driven, and hybrid approaches.

1) *Direct Measurement-Based Methods*: In direct measurement-based methods, SoH is determined from measured physical battery parameters. One example is the Coulomb counting method, where charge and discharge data are used to estimate usable capacity. Another example is internal resistance measurement, where changes in resistance are used as indicators of degradation [1], [13].

Fig. 1. SoH estimation method [1].

Fig. 2. Framework of a deep learning method for SoH estimation [4].

2) *Model-Based Methods*: Model-based methods use mathematical representations of battery behavior. Equivalent circuit models (ECMs), for example, represent the battery using electrical elements such as resistors and capacitors. Changes in model parameters over time can indicate battery degradation and support SoH estimation [3].

3) *Data-Driven Methods*: Data-driven methods have gained attention because they do not require a detailed physical model of the battery. Instead, they use measured operational data, such as voltage, current, temperature, and impedance, to learn the relationship between battery behavior and health state [3]. These methods include machine learning and deep learning approaches that can capture nonlinear relationships. However, their performance strongly depends on the quality, representativeness, and operating conditions of the training data.

Overall, no single SoH estimation method is suitable for every application. The appropriate method depends on data availability, system complexity, and the required level of accuracy. In modern battery applications, combinations of physical models and data-driven methods are increasingly considered [1].

D. Deep Learning Approaches for SoH Estimation

Deep learning methods learn patterns directly from large datasets. After training, a model can estimate SoH from measured battery variables such as voltage, current, temperature, or impedance [1]. Fig. 2 illustrates a general deep learning framework for battery SoH estimation.

The process typically begins with data collection from sensors, battery history, or laboratory measurements. The data are then preprocessed by removing noise, cleaning invalid values, and extracting useful features. A suitable model architecture

Fig. 3. 1D-CNN structure [14].

is selected according to the data type. Common architectures include artificial neural networks (ANNs), recurrent neural networks (RNNs), long short-term memory networks (LSTMs), convolutional neural networks (CNNs), and hybrid models. After training, the model is evaluated using regression metrics to assess its prediction accuracy and practical applicability [4].

Common deep learning methods for SoH estimation include the following:

- *Artificial neural networks:* ANNs are among the earliest neural network models used for SoH estimation. They can learn relationships between input variables, such as voltage, current, and temperature, and the remaining capacity of the battery.
- *RNN and LSTM models:* Because battery behavior evolves over time, models capable of processing sequential data are useful. RNNs and LSTMs can account for long-term dependencies in time-series data, making them suitable for analyzing capacity fade across cycles [4].
- *Convolutional neural networks:* CNNs can extract features from ordered signals, such as voltage-time curves, capacity-time curves, and impedance spectra. These models can identify hidden patterns in measured data [4].

The main advantages of deep learning methods are their ability to model nonlinear behavior, their reduced dependence on exact physical modeling, and their ability to use operational data. Their main limitations include dependence on the quantity and quality of training data, sensitivity to operating conditions, and higher computational requirements.

E. 1D-CNN Method for SoH Estimation

Among CNN-based approaches, 1D-CNN is well suited for battery applications because many battery measurements are ordered as time-series or frequency-series data. A 1D-CNN can automatically extract degradation-related features from raw or preprocessed battery signals [3]. A typical 1D-CNN structure includes an input layer, convolutional layers, pooling layers, fully connected layers, and an output layer, as illustrated in Fig. 3 [14].

In the convolutional layer, filters move over the input signal and extract local patterns. The convolution operation can be expressed as

$$x_t^l = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{l-1}} \text{conv1D}(\omega_{it}^{l-1}, s_i^{l-1}) + b_t^l, \quad (3)$$

where x_t^l , ω_{it}^{l-1} , s_i^{l-1} , and b_t^l denote the neuron input, convolution kernel, output from the previous layer, and bias term, respectively.

To increase nonlinear learning capability, the rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function is commonly used:

$$\text{ReLU}(x) = \max(0, x). \quad (4)$$

A pooling layer is then used to reduce data dimensionality and help prevent overfitting. It can be defined as

$$s_t^l = \max_{(t-1)H+1 \leq j \leq tH} (s_j^{l-1}), \quad (5)$$

where s_t^l is the output of the pooling layer. Overall, 1D-CNN models can extract features from ordered battery data and learn nonlinear relationships between battery measurements and SoH [14].

F. Metrics for Assessment

Several statistical metrics can be used to evaluate the performance of SoH estimation models. These metrics measure the difference between predicted and actual values [14], [15].

Root mean square error (RMSE) measures the standard deviation of prediction errors:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - y'_i)^2}, \quad (6)$$

where y_i is the actual value, y'_i is the predicted value, and n is the number of samples.

Mean absolute error (MAE) measures the average absolute difference between predicted and actual values:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - y'_i|. \quad (7)$$

Mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) evaluates prediction error as a percentage:

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i - y'_i}{y_i} \right|. \quad (8)$$

III. ANALYSIS

The deep learning model used in this study is a 1D-CNN trained and tested on electrochemical impedance spectroscopy data. Before model training, the original dataset was cleaned and transformed into complete impedance spectra suitable for neural network input.

A. Dataset Description

The dataset contains EIS measurements collected from lithium-ion battery cells during cycling experiments. Each observation represents the impedance response of a battery at a specific cycle number and state of charge (SoC). The dataset was obtained from [16].

The original dataset contains approximately 313,675 observations from 34 battery cells under multiple test conditions. The main variables include the battery cell identifier *Cell_ID*,

Fig. 4. SoH distribution.

Fig. 5. SoH versus $nCycle$.

the test-condition identifier LCT_ID , the number of charge-discharge cycles $nCycle$, the state of charge during measurement SoC , the excitation frequency $freq_Hz$, the real impedance component $Zreal_ohm$, the imaginary impedance component $Zimag_ohm$, and the state of health SoH . In this study, SoH is the target variable for model training. The value of $nCycle$ ranges from 0 to 5900, with an average of approximately 1270 cycles.

An initial exploratory analysis was conducted to understand the distribution of SoH values and the degradation behavior of the analyzed cells. As shown in Fig. 4, most SoH values are concentrated close to 1.0, indicating that many observations correspond to early stages of degradation.

The relationship between SoH and $nCycle$ was also examined for different test conditions. Fig. 5 shows a gradual reduction in SoH as the number of cycles increases. However, the degradation rates differ across test conditions, which indicates that operating conditions influence battery aging behavior.

The EIS measurements consist of impedance values measured across multiple frequencies. For each battery state defined by $Cell_ID$, $nCycle$, and SoC , the impedance spectrum contains 61 frequency points. Therefore, each training sample consists of

61 frequency measurements with two features, $Zreal_ohm$ and $Zimag_ohm$, resulting in an input tensor with shape ($samples, 61, 2$).

B. Dataset Processing

Some entries in the dataset contain invalid SoH values equal to -1, representing missing or invalid measurements. These entries were removed before model training. The final dataset used for training and testing contains 3026 valid impedance spectra, with SoH as the target variable.

To avoid information leakage between battery histories, the dataset was split based on battery cells rather than individual samples. First, all unique $Cell_ID$ values were extracted. The cells were then randomly shuffled. In total, 80% of the cells were used for training, and the remaining 20% were used for testing. This procedure ensures that the model is evaluated on completely unseen battery cells, providing a more realistic estimate of model generalization.

The final preprocessing step was feature normalization. This process standardizes the range of independent variables and provides a consistent scale for model learning. The impedance values were standardized using the *StandardScaler* function from the scikit-learn library [17]. Standardization can be written as

$$X_{std} = \frac{X_{original} - \mu}{\sigma}, \quad (9)$$

where X_{std} is the standardized feature value, $X_{original}$ is the original feature value, μ is the mean, and σ is the standard deviation. Standardization was applied to both $Zreal_ohm$ and $Zimag_ohm$.

C. Model Architecture

The model architecture was implemented in PyTorch as a 1D-CNN for predicting battery SoH from EIS spectra [14]. Each input sample consisted of 61 impedance points with two features: the real impedance component ($Zreal_ohm$) and the imaginary impedance component ($Zimag_ohm$). Thus, the input shape was $(61, 2)$.

The network contained three convolutional layers with 16, 32, and 64 filters, respectively. Each convolutional layer used a kernel size of 3. A max-pooling layer was applied after each convolutional layer to reduce dimensionality and preserve the most relevant extracted features. The resulting feature maps were flattened and passed through a fully connected layer with 64 neurons. A dropout layer with a rate of 0.3 was included before the final output layer to reduce overfitting. The final layer consisted of a single neuron that produced the predicted SoH value as a continuous output.

ReLU activation functions were used after each convolutional layer and before the fully connected output stage. The 1D-CNN architecture was selected because EIS measurements can be interpreted as ordered sequential signals across frequency, allowing convolutional filters to learn local impedance patterns associated with battery degradation.

Fig. 6. Training and validation loss.

D. Model Training

The model was trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 and the mean squared error (MSE) loss function. Training was performed for 40 epochs with a batch size of 64.

The Adam optimizer was selected because it uses adaptive learning rates, performs well with sparse gradients, and has relatively low memory requirements. A step-based learning-rate scheduler was applied to gradually reduce the learning rate during training, improving convergence stability and supporting better generalization.

To monitor training, both training and validation losses were evaluated at each epoch. The training loss indicates how well the model fits the training data, while the validation loss reflects the model's ability to generalize to unseen data. As shown in Fig. 6, both curves decrease during training, indicating that the model learns from the input data.

E. Model Results

The model performance was assessed by comparing predicted SoH values with actual SoH values. Fig. 7 shows the relationship between predicted and actual values. The red diagonal line represents the ideal case, where predictions exactly match the true values. The blue points represent the model predictions.

The predicted values generally follow the overall trend of the actual SoH values. The trained model achieved an MAE of 0.02946 and an RMSE of 0.06752, indicating relatively low average prediction error.

In addition to MAE and RMSE, the coefficient of determination (R^2) was evaluated to assess how well the model explains the variance of the target variable. The obtained R^2 value was -0.851. This result indicates that, although the model achieves low average error, it does not fully capture the variability of SoH values across the dataset.

Fig. 7. Predicted versus actual SoH values.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Results Discussion

The training and validation losses in Fig. 6 decrease over the training process. The reduction in training loss shows that the model improves its fit to the training data. The decreasing validation loss suggests that the model can generalize to unseen data without strong evidence of overfitting during the observed training process. Overall, this behavior indicates that the CNN model can learn meaningful patterns from the impedance spectra.

The comparison between predicted and actual SoH values in Fig. 7 shows that most predictions follow the general trend of the true values. This suggests that the model captures part of the relationship between impedance measurements and battery health. However, deviations from the ideal diagonal line are also visible, indicating that prediction accuracy is not uniform across all samples.

The SoH distribution plays an important role in this behavior. As shown in Fig. 4, most samples are concentrated in the high-SoH range. This imbalance can cause the model to learn dominant high-SoH patterns more effectively than less frequent lower-SoH patterns. As a result, the model tends to produce predictions within a narrower range than the true SoH values.

Although the MAE and RMSE values indicate relatively low average prediction error, they do not fully describe the model's ability to represent the full spread of SoH values. The negative R^2 value confirms that the model does not fully capture the target-variable variance. Therefore, the results should be interpreted as evidence that the model can learn the general degradation trend, but not as evidence of complete predictive reliability across all degradation stages.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the 1D-CNN model can extract useful information from EIS data for battery SoH estimation. However, improvements in data balance, model generalization, and representation of lower-SoH conditions

would be necessary before the approach could be considered robust for broader practical use.

B. Model Limitations

Although the proposed CNN model achieved relatively low average prediction errors, several limitations should be considered.

First, the usable dataset for model training and testing was limited. Complete impedance spectra were extracted from the original dataset, but this processing reduced the number of usable samples. The final dataset contained 3026 valid impedance spectra, while the original dataset contained 313,675 observations and approximately 5142 possible spectra.

Second, the SoH distribution was imbalanced. Most measurements represented relatively healthy batteries, which limited the model's exposure to later degradation stages. This imbalance likely reduced prediction accuracy for lower-SoH samples.

Third, the model was trained using impedance measurements collected under controlled laboratory conditions. In real-world applications, additional operating factors, such as temperature variation, mechanical vibration, usage history, and charging behavior, may influence the actual SoH of a battery.

C. Future Improvements

Future work could address these limitations by incorporating larger and more balanced datasets with a wider range of SoH values. Additional operating conditions, such as temperature and usage patterns, could also be included to improve real-world applicability. Furthermore, physics-informed features could be added to strengthen the model's ability to represent battery degradation mechanisms. These improvements could enhance both the robustness and accuracy of EIS-based SoH estimation.

V. CONCLUSION

This study developed a deep learning model based on a one-dimensional convolutional neural network for estimating the state of health of lithium-ion batteries using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy data. The original dataset consisted of 313,675 observations from 34 battery cells, which were processed into 3026 valid impedance spectra for model training and evaluation.

The proposed model learned the general relationship between impedance spectra and battery degradation. It achieved an MAE of 0.02946 and an RMSE of 0.06752, indicating relatively low average prediction error. However, the negative R^2 value shows that the model did not fully capture the variability of SoH values across the dataset.

The results suggest that 1D-CNN models can be useful for identifying general degradation trends from EIS data. At the same time, the study highlights the importance of balanced data, broader operating conditions, and improved model generalization. Overall, this work demonstrates the potential of deep learning for battery-health estimation and provides a basis for further development of data-driven SoH prediction methods.

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